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5 **Revalorization of sheep-wool keratin for the preparation of fully** 6 **biobased printable inks**

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8 **Lorena Ugarte**^{1,2,*}, **Borja Fernández-d’Arlas**³, **Izaskun Larraza**², **Garazi Berra**², **Nagore Gabilondo**²
9 **and Arantxa Eceiza**^{2,*}

10 ¹ Department of Graphical Design and Project Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Gipuzkoa, Eibar section. Av. Otaola
11 29, 20600 Eibar, Spain; lorena.ugarte@ehu.eus

12 ² GMT Materials+Technologies Research Group. Department of Chemistry and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of
13 Engineering, Gipuzkoa, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Plaza Europa 1, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián,
14 Spain; izaskun.larraza@ehu.eus, garazi.berra@ehu.eus, arantxa.eceiza@ehu.eus

15 ³ Evolgene Genomics S.L., Av. Tolosa 76, Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain; b.fernandez-darlas@evolgene.com

16 * Correspondence: lorena.ugarte@ehu.eus; arantxa.eceiza@ehu.eus
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18 **Abstract:** Sheep wool waste has become a problem affecting the environment, as today the wool
19 of most species has no commercial application and is considered a waste product. Sheep's wool
20 is mainly composed of keratin which, due to its protein nature and multiple functional groups, has
21 attracted great interest in applications such as support materials in tissue engineering, bioactive
22 materials, and targeted drug delivery. Support materials can be fabricated by 3D printing by
23 syringe extrusion. However, keratin is not suitable for this technique as it does not present proper
24 rheological characteristics. Alginate, a biopolymer derived from brown seaweed, offers a wide
25 range of viscosities at room temperature and offers good performance in 3D printing. Thus, keratin
26 and alginate-based mixtures, due to their properties and ecoefficiency, are interesting candidates
27 to prepare 3D-printed scaffolds. The aim of this work was to develop fully biobased printable inks
28 containing keratin, alginate, salvia extracts, and cellulose nanofibers. In a first stage, keratose,
29 an oxidized form of keratin, was obtained from sheep wool by a clean extraction methodology,
30 and the miscibility and viscosity of keratose-alginate mixtures were assessed. In a second stage,
31 biobased inks were prepared parting from miscible keratose-alginate mixtures. Flow analysis,
32 spectromechanical analysis, and recovery tests were carried out to analyze the effect of the ink
33 formulation over rheological parameters and printability. Mesh and cylinder geometries were 3D
34 printed and their mechanical properties, as well as shape fidelity and self-standing ability, were
35 assessed.
36

37 **Keywords:** 3D printing; keratin; keratose; alginate; CNF; rheology
38

39 **1. Introduction** 40

41 The appearance of synthetic fibers in 1880 gave place to a progressive drop in the presence of
42 wool fibers in the textile industry. In 2020, wool represented only a 1% of the global textile fibers
43 market share [1]. In 2019, The European Union possessed the second largest ovine livestock
44 population, with United Kingdom (26.8 %), Spain (18.6 %), Rumania (11.4%) and Greece (10.8 %)
45 heading the list [2]. The ovine livestock is mainly intended for meat industry and, to a lesser extent,
46 for milk production. Although there are some wools that are very appreciated in the textile industry,
47 such as Merino sheep soft and fine wool, the majority of wool has no commercial applications due
48 to its low quality, and it is considered an agricultural solid waste, being landfilled or incinerated.
49 For example, the wool considered in this work comes from “Latxa” sheep, a domestic sheep native
50 to Basque Country. Its wool is comprised by thick fibers, even thicker than 100 microns, resulting
51 in a coarse material. In this scenario, more than 200,000 tons of wool are generated each year in
52 the European Union [3]. This results in a reduction in the profit for stockbreeders since, together

53 with shear expenses, costs coming from residue management should also be taken into account.
54 Moreover, the mentioned waste management practices are non-ecofriendly and generate a
55 negative impact on the environment.

56 The main component of wool is keratin. Keratin comprises a sulfur-rich range of proteins,
57 abundant in many living tissues, such as skin or hair [4]. Among others, protein based polymers
58 are considered as the most ecoefficient bioplastics concerning their potential applications over
59 the generated environmental impacts [5]. Most of the keratin extractive processes found in
60 literature are laborious and expensive. However, new eco-friendly methods are being developed,
61 such as microwave assisted [6], deep eutectic solvents based [7], or microbial and enzymatic
62 extraction processes [8]. In a previous work, we reported a clean oxidative keratin extraction
63 methodology from "Latxa" sheep wool based on hydrogen peroxide [9], by which keratin in the
64 oxidized form called keratose is obtained. Natural keratin presents intra and intermolecular
65 disulfide bonds, making it chemically stable and water insoluble. In keratose, in turn, disulfide
66 bonds are converted into cysteic acids, making it water soluble. The reported extraction
67 methodology would generate a reduction on the environmental impact associated to this process,
68 increasing the ecoefficiency of derived materials. Moreover, it would enable a large scale
69 production and revalorization in sectors such as bioplastics or biomedicine [10].

70 Keratinous materials have the potential to be used in biomedical applications [11-14], such as
71 scaffolds, due to their protein nature and the presence in human tissues. A recent research
72 conducted by C.W. Lin et al. [15] highlighted that keratin scaffolds promoted mother cell adhesion,
73 proliferation and differentiation while, also favoring the epithelialization of damaged dermal tissue.
74 Other works revealed that cells such as fibroblasts are able to reproduce satisfactorily on keratin
75 scaffolds, suggesting an appropriate biocompatibility [16]. It has been reported in literature that
76 3D scaffolds are more active than 2D scaffolds when tested in vitro with neural stem cells [17].
77 Thus, it can be said that morphology, dimensionality, accessibility and porosity are critical
78 characteristics of scaffolds. Supplying an appropriate quantity of nutrients and oxygen to
79 implanted cells is crucial for their survival and 3D scaffolds offer larger surface area for cellular
80 adhesion and proliferation, while they allow a flow of nutrients and oxygen to the cells [18].

81 Nowadays there exist several methods for scaffold manufacturing, such as electrospinning, tissue
82 decellularization, lyophilization or additive manufacturing [19,20]. Additive manufacturing, also
83 known as 3D printing, has attracted much attention due to the possibility of manufacturing parts
84 on demand, with complex and personalized design. Within 3D printing, several techniques have
85 been developed, such as fused deposition modeling (FDM), stereolithography (SLA), selective
86 laser sintering (SLS) and syringe extrusion printing (SEP). SEP offers the advantage to work
87 directly with the material in suspension, known as ink, overcoming the limitation of available
88 materials range and the need of aggressive processing conditions, such as heat or the use of
89 organic solvents, needed in other additive manufacturing techniques [21,22]. SEP technique also
90 offers the possibility of incorporating biologic material such as cells to the ink. This specific SEP
91 technique takes the name of bioprinting and the ink is designed as bioink.

92 Printability defines a material's suitability to be printed by SEP and it lies mainly on the rheological
93 properties such as viscosity, shear-thinning ability, extrusion, viscoelastic shear moduli, elastic
94 recovery and shear stress [23,24]. An ink would be printable when it presents extrudability,
95 defined as the ability of an ink to flow through a nozzle, and shape fidelity to reproduce a CAD
96 design by forming a self-standing and non-spreading structure. In consequence, rheological
97 properties of inks need to be tailored. In this scenario, alginate biopolymer is an interesting
98 candidate due to the wide range of viscosity at room temperature at which it can be found [25,26].
99 Alginate, a brown-seaweed derived biomaterial, is known for its biocompatibility [27],
100 biodegradability [28] and mechanical integrity [29]. Keratin-alginate mixtures are an interesting
101 approach to combine the properties of both components. For example, Silva et al. developed
102 hybrid hydrogels based on keratin and alginate aimed at tissue engineering applications [30].
103 They proved that the obtained material offered a combination of chemical and mechanical
104 stability, biocompatibility and cell viability. The rheological modulating ability of nanoentities such
105 as cellulose nanocrystals or cellulose nanofibers has also been studied. For example, Markstedt

106 et al. prepared alginate-nanocellulose bioinks and concluded that nanocellulose conferred the
107 desired rheological behavior while alginate provided mechanical performance [31]. Similarly,
108 Muller et al. converted an alginate sulfate based bioink in a printable material by incorporating
109 nanocellulose [32].

110 Plant extracts have also received attention in the biomedical field since they can be natural
111 sources of active agents, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and phenolic compounds. For
112 example, *Salvia officinalis L.* is a rich source of polyphenols with promising bioactivity, antioxidant
113 and anticancer activities [33]. Indeed, in previous works we demonstrated the antibacterial effect
114 of *Salvia officinalis L.* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas*
115 *aeruginosa*, when added to starch or polyurethane matrices [34, 35]. Moreover, similar to
116 cellulose nanoentities, it has been reported that *Salvia officinalis L.* extracts can act as surfactants
117 [36]. Although previously mentioned research works have demonstrated the potential of keratin
118 and keratin-alginate blends in biomedical applications, no works concerning 3D printing of keratin-
119 containing inks have been published to the best of authors' knowledge. In this work, firstly keratin
120 in form of keratose was obtained from "Latxa" sheep wool residues, by applying the clean
121 extraction methodology aforementioned, and it was characterized in terms of Fourier Transform
122 Infrared Spectroscopy and thermal performance. Then, keratose-alginate mixtures were analyzed
123 in terms of miscibility and viscosity. Finally, keratose-alginate mixtures were loaded with *Salvia*
124 *officinalis L.*, and their suitability as inks for SEP was explored performing a deep analysis on the
125 rheological behavior by means of flow analysis, spectromechanical analysis and three interval
126 thixotropy tests. Moreover, inks containing cellulose nanofibers were also considered and their
127 impact on inks rheological behavior was analyzed. Finally, mesh and cylinder geometries were
128 printed and the impact of rheological parameters on shape fidelity and self-standing ability was
129 assessed. Moreover, the mechanical performance of printed parts was evaluated by compressive
130 tests. The valorization of keratin rich sheep wool residues for the preparation of fully biobased
131 inks would promote the implementation of sustainable extraction processes, while promoting the
132 use of sustainable raw materials and contributing to Circular Economy and Ecodesign.
133

134 **2. Materials and Methods**

135 *2.1. Materials*

136 Keratose was extracted from "Latxa" sheep wool, supplied by local stockbreeders. Hydrogen
137 peroxide (30%, Panreac) and HCl (37%, Panreac) were employed in keratose extraction process.
138 Sodium alginate powder from brown algae with medium viscosity (A2033) and molecular weight
139 of $2.4 \times 10^5 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ [33] was kindly supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. The simplified chemical structures
140 of sodium alginate and keratose are proposed in Figure 1a and Figure 1b, respectively. Freeze
141 dried cellulose nanofibers (CNF) with length of several micrometers and diameter between 50-
142 200 nm [37], were provided by the University of Maine (lot.9004-34-6).
143
144

145 *2.2. Obtaining of salvia extract*

146 *Salvia* extract was obtained according to the method described in literature [35]. In brief,
147 previously grinded *Salvia officinalis L.* plant was infused in boiling water (25 mg mL^{-1}) for 5 min.
148 The obtained suspension was filtered and the obtained liquid phase was collected and lyophilized
149 ($-80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 0.1 mbar) for 48 h in a Telstar LyoQuest equipment. The *salvia* extract was obtained as
150 the dried product after the freeze-drying process.
151
152

153 *2.3. Extraction of keratose*

154 Keratose was extracted from "Latxa" sheep wool according to the aforementioned oxidative
155 method with hydrogen peroxide [9]. In brief, previously washed and milled wool was immersed in
156 hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2 , 1.5 M) for 2 h at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Wool/ H_2O_2 ratio was kept constant at 50 g L^{-1}
157
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159 and pH was set at 11. The obtained liquor was filtered, and the keratose solution was acidified
 160 with HCl for keratose precipitation. Thereafter, the acid medium was substituted with water and
 161 isopropanol to wash the keratose. Finally, the keratose was lyophilized (-80 °C, 0.1 mbar, 48 h)
 162 in a Telstar LyoQuest equipment for posterior utilization.

163
 164 **Figure 1.** Schematic representation of (a) sodium alginate and (b) keratose chemical structures
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166 **2.4. Preparation of keratose-alginate mixtures**

167
 168 For the preparation of keratose (K) and alginate (A) mixtures, first keratose was dispersed in
 169 distilled water using an ultrasonic tip for 3 h at 30% amplitude. Then, alginate powder was added
 170 and the solution was subjected to mechanical agitation. The prepared mixtures were labelled as
 171 M X-Y where X denoted the K:A weight ratio over the solid content of the mixture and Y the total
 172 solid content (wt.%). Table 1 shows designation, composition and solid content of the analyzed
 173 mixtures, together with viscosity at 0.2 s⁻¹ (considered as zero-shear rate viscosity), as well as
 174 consistency index and flow index values obtained from flow curves and power-law model fitting,
 175 respectively.

176
 177 **Table 1.** Designation, keratose (K) and alginate (A) content, solid content, viscosity at 0.2 s⁻¹, and power-
 178 law model fitting parameters (consistency index, flow index and R²)
 179

Designation	K (wt%)	A (wt%)	Solid content (wt %)	Viscosity at 0.2 s ⁻¹ (Pa.s)	Consistency index (Pa.s ⁿ)	Flow index	R ²
M-1:1-6	3	3	6	111	48	0.500	0.99419
M-1:1-10	5	5	10	506	244	0.512	0.99133
M-2:1-6	4	2	6	53	21	0.447	0.98323
M-2:1-10	6,7	3,3	10	80	48	0.396	0.99515
M-2:1-15	10	5	15	2383	756	0.185	0.99935
M-3:1-6	4,5	1,5	6	43	17	0.396	0.99517
M-3:1-10	7,5	2,5	10	53	28	0.575	0.98681

180
 181 **2.5. Preparation of inks**
 182

183 The preparation procedure of keratose-alginate-salvia extract inks was similar to keratose-
 184 alginate mixtures. First, salvia extract was dissolved in distilled water at a 10 wt.% content with
 185 respect to keratose. Then, keratose was added and the mixture was dispersed using an ultrasonic
 186 tip for 3 h at 30% amplitude. Subsequently, alginate powder was added and the solution was
 187 subjected to mechanical agitation. Inks were labelled as I-X-Y where X denoted the K:A weight
 188 ratio over the total weight of the ink, and Y the solid content (wt.%). For inks containing CNF, dry
 189 CNF was incorporated in previously prepared keratose-alginate-salvia extract inks, at a 2 wt.%

190 with respect to the total solid content. The resulting mixture was dispersed in a high shear mixer
191 (Ultraturrax®) for 15 minutes. Inks containing CNF were labelled as I-X-Y-CNF. Designation and
192 composition of the prepared inks are gathered in Table 2.

193

194 **Table 2.** Designation, keratose (K), alginate (A), salvia (S) and cellulose nanofiber (CNF) content of prepared
195 inks.

Designation	K (wt%)	A (wt%)	S (wt %)	CNF (wt%)
I-1:1-10	5	5	0.3	-
I-1:1-10-CNF	5	5	0.3	2
I-2:1-15	10	5	0.6	-
I-2:1-15-CNF	10	5	0.6	2

196

197 2.6. 3D printing

198

199 To observe the impact of rheological parameters over the 3D printing performance, mesh and
200 cylinder geometries were printed using the prepared inks in a Voladora 3D printer (Tumaker S.L.,
201 Spain) modified for layer-by-layer syringe extrusion printing. Specifically, a mechanical piston that
202 moved the embolus of a syringe replaced the fused deposition modeling (FDM) head. This
203 allowed the extrusion of the ink through a needle in both axes x and y. Mesh geometry of 20 mm
204 x 20 mm (wide x length) with 2 mm height, with square-shaped pores of 5 mm x 5 mm, and
205 cylinder geometry of 10 mm diameter and 5 mm height were CAD modeled (Figure 5). Parts were
206 printed at room temperature, at a speed of 6 mm s⁻¹ and using a 0.8 mm diameter needle. Layer
207 height of 0.2 mm and rectilinear filling pattern were chosen. Finally, printed geometries were
208 freeze-dried at -80 °C and 0.1 mbar for 48 h to obtain porous scaffolds.

209

210 2.7. Characterization techniques

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212 2.7.1. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

213

214 The functional groups of keratose and alginate were analyzed by Fourier transform infrared
215 spectroscopy (FTIR). A Nicolet Nexus spectrometer provided with a MKII Golden Gate accessory
216 (Specac) was used, with a diamond crystal at a nominal incidence angle of 45°, and ZnSe lens.
217 Spectra were recorded in attenuated reflection (ATR) mode in the range of 4000-650 cm⁻¹,
218 averaging 64 scans with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹.

219

220 2.7.2. Thermogravimetric analysis

221

222 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of keratose was performed on a TGA/SDTA 851 Metler Toledo
223 equipment in order to evaluate thermal stability. Pure keratose sample was heated from room
224 temperature to 700 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹, under nitrogen atmosphere.

225

226 2.7.3. Rheological measurements

227

228 Viscosity of keratose-alginate mixtures was analyzed by flow test. Rheological behavior of the
229 prepared ink formulations was analyzed by flow test, oscillatory shear stress sweep and three-
230 interval-thixotropy tests, using a Haake Viscotester iQ (Thermo Scientific). Tests were carried out
231 by plate-plate geometry (P35/Al adapter), employing plates of 35 mm diameter. Working gap and
232 temperature were set at 1 mm and 25 °C, respectively.

233 For flow tests, shear rate sweeps from 0.2 to 1000 s⁻¹ were performed. Prior to each
234 measurement, samples were equilibrated for 40 s at 0.2 s⁻¹. Flow index and consistency index of
235 each ink were calculated from Power Law (equation 1).

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$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = K\dot{\gamma}^{n-1} \quad (\text{equation 1})$$

where η is the viscosity (Pa·s), $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate (s^{-1}), K is the consistency index ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}^n$) and n is the flow index (dimensionless).

Spectromechanical analysis was carried out by dynamic oscillatory shear stress sweep tests, working in a shear stress range of 10 to 3000 Pa. The evolution of storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') with shear stress was determined. G' and G'' values were determined at 10 Pa shear stress. Yield point was set at the point of deviation of G' from linearity, as proposed by Cyriac et al. [38]. Flow point, on the other hand, is defined as the crossover point for G' and G'' . Last, structure recovery was analyzed by three-interval-thixotropy tests. Viscosity values were measured at a first shear rate interval of 0.2 s^{-1} during 100 s, followed by a second shear rate interval of 50 s^{-1} for 100 s, finishing with a third shear rate interval at the same conditions as in the first stage. For the determination of the structural recovery capacity of the inks, a relation of the ink's viscosity on the first and third shear rate intervals was calculated as expressed in equation 2.

$$\text{Structural Recovery} = \frac{\eta_{3I}}{\eta_{1I}} \cdot 100 \quad (\text{equation 2})$$

where η_{1I} is the viscosity of the material on the first shear rate interval and η_{3I} is the viscosity of the material on the third shear rate interval, both measured after 60 seconds of the beginning of the interval.

2.7.3. Mechanical properties

Compressive properties of the printed specimens were tested at room temperature, in a Universal testing machine (Instron 5967) equipped with 500 N load cell at a crosshead speed of 2 mm min^{-1} . 3D printed cylinder shaped specimens were compressed until 60% deformation. According to ASTM D 1621-16 standard, compressive strength (σ_c) was taken as the stress at the yield point and compressive modulus (E_c) was considered as the slope at the elastic region of stress-strain curve. Densification strain (ϵ_d) was calculated as the strain value at the intersection point between the stress plateau and the densification slope. Results were averaged from at least four measurements.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Keratose and alginate characterization

FTIR results of keratose (Figure 2a) showed typical spectra of proteins. Bands related with amide I, II and III regions were identified in $1700\text{-}1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. Amide I band, due to C=O stretching, was observed at 1657 cm^{-1} . Amide II band was identified at 1547 cm^{-1} , mainly related to out of phase combination of N-H in plane bending and C-N stretching vibration. Amide III band due to C-N stretching was identified at 1240 cm^{-1} [39, 40]. According to literature, the identified wavenumbers for amide bands would be indicative of a predominant α -helix conformation of keratose [41,42]. This also agrees with the mammalian origin of keratin used in this work [40]. Apart from amide regions, bands corresponding to N-H stretching (3296 cm^{-1}) and C-H stretching (2925 cm^{-1}) were also identified. Also, a band located at 1042 cm^{-1} and a shoulder located at 1174 cm^{-1} were identified, and were related to the presence of sulfinate groups [10]. Concerning the spectrum corresponding to alginate, a broad band related to O-H stretching vibration was observed at around $3500\text{-}3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The band at 2925 cm^{-1} was assigned to C-H stretching and the band at 1591 cm^{-1} was related to carboxylate - (C=O)-O- asymmetric stretching. The band at 1406 cm^{-1} belonged to C-OH deformation vibration and carboxylate -(C=O)-O- symmetric

289 stretching. Finally, the band at 1026 cm⁻¹ was assigned to C-O stretching vibration of pyranose
290 rings [43].

291 **Figure 2.** a) FTIR spectra of keratose and alginate , and b) TG (continuous line) and DTG (dashed line)
292 curves of keratose and alginate
293

294 Thermal stability of keratose and alginate was analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis. Obtained
295 thermogram (TG) and the derivative (DTG) are shown in Figure 2b. For keratose, three thermal
296 degradation stages were observed. The first one, at 75 °C, was assigned to the release of
297 moisture and volatile compounds. The second one, beginning around 200 °C, was related to the
298 degradation of side chains, in good accordance to Aluigi et al. who analyzed the thermal
299 degradation of keratin extracted from merino wool [44]. The shoulder observed at around 220 °C
300 in this endotherm was related to the removal of sulfur containing gases. The last stage, starting
301 at 444 °C, could be related to pyrolytic decomposition [45]. The maximum degradation rate,
302 defined as the minimum of DTG curve was determined at 325 °C. A char amount of 20 wt.% was
303 measured. In the case of alginate, two-stage thermal degradation was observed. The first stage,
304 beginning at 100 °C, could be related to absorbed water and volatile compounds. The second
305 one, in the range of 195-270 °C was related with disentanglement of polymeric network [46]. A
306 final char amount of 24 wt.% was determined for alginate, in good agreement with literature [47].
307 The maximum degradation rate was measured at 212 °C.
308

309 3.2. Keratose-alginate mixtures characterization

310

311 Prior to the preparation of inks, the miscibility of keratose-alginate aqueous mixtures was
 312 considered. In a qualitative approach, both the effect of K:A weight ratio and the effect of solid
 313 content were analyzed. Photographs of the mixtures are shown in Figure 3a. Concerning K:A
 314 weight ratio, it was observed that for a constant solid content of 10 wt.%, the system was miscible
 315 until a K:A weight ratio of 3:1. With higher keratose contents, the system split in two phases.
 316 Concerning solid content, it was varied from 6 to 14 wt.% keeping K:A weight ratio constant at the
 317 miscibility limit of 3:1. It was observed that the system was miscible until a solid content of
 318 10 wt.%. At lower K:A ratios the system was miscible up to a solid content of 15 wt.%, such as
 319 M-2:1-15. Thus, it was concluded that an increase in K:A weight ratio or in solid content hindered
 320 miscibility. For further characterization, miscible mixtures listed in Table 1 were considered.
 321 Results concerning flow test of miscible systems are shown in Figure 3c-e and Table 1. All
 322 samples showed pseudoplastic behavior, evidenced by flow index values in 0-1 range. Analyzing
 323 the effect of K:A ratio, it was observed that viscosity values increased as K:A ratio decreased in
 324 mixtures with both 6 wt.% and 10 wt.% solid content, Figure 3c and 3d respectively, probably
 325 related to the higher content of alginate. The same effect was qualitatively observed in Figure 3b,
 326 where mixtures with 6 wt.% solid content at different K:A ratios are shown. Analyzing these results
 327 it can be concluded that the increase of alginate content resulted in inks with high viscosity, which
 328 may be related with the high molecular weight of alginate ($2.4 \times 10^5 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) [48, 49]. Concerning
 329 solid content, Figure 3e, it was verified that it played a vital role concerning viscosity of the
 330 mixtures [50], since M-2:1-15 showed the highest zero viscosity value (2383 Pa.s) among all
 331 analyzed samples.
 332

333 **Figure 3.** (a) Photographs of keratose-alginate mixtures, (b) qualitative evolution of viscosity in keratose-
 334 alginate mixtures with 6 wt.% solid content and different K:A ratios, and the evolution of viscosity as a
 335 function of shear rate analyzing (c) the effect of K:A ratio in keratose-alginate mixtures with 6 wt.% solid

336 content, (d) the effect of K:A ratio in keratose-alginate mixtures with 10 wt.% solid content, and (e) the effect
 337 of variation of solid content in keratose-alginate mixtures with K:A ratio of 2:1.
 338

339 Consistency index values (Table 1) showed a direct relationship with the alginate content of the
 340 mixtures, in concordance with zero-shear viscosity values. The highest values were measured for
 341 M-1:1-10 (244 Pa.sⁿ) and M-2:1-15 (756 Pa.sⁿ) samples. Concerning the effect of keratose in the
 342 mixtures, a notorious decrease of consistency index values was observed as keratose content
 343 increased, when comparing mixtures with the same solid content. With respect to flow index
 344 values (Table 1), values did not show a direct relationship with solid content. As a general trend,
 345 values decreased with keratose incorporation, improving the pseudoplastic behavior of the
 346 mixtures. M-3:1-10 sample did not follow this tendency, probably because this mixture was on the
 347 limit of miscibility and it would have influenced the rheological behavior.

348 From this preliminary study, it was concluded that samples M-1:1-10 and M-2:1-15 showed the
 349 highest potential to be used as inks, since high zero-shear viscosity and consistency index values
 350 would result in good shape fidelity [51]. On the other hand, results suggested that increasing the
 351 solid content would be an effective strategy to maximize the keratose incorporation on the inks.
 352

353 3.3. Rheological characterization of inks

354
 355 Rheological values determined for the inks are gathered in Table 3. Flow curves of prepared inks
 356 are shown in Figure 4a.

357 **Table 3.** Viscosity, consistency and flow indexes, G' and G'' moduli, tanδ, yield point, flow point and structural
 358 recovery (SR) values of prepared inks.
 359

Ink	Viscosity at 0.2 s ⁻¹ (Pa.s)	Consistency index (Pa.s ⁿ)	Flow index	R ²	G' (Pa)	G'' (Pa)	tan δ	Yield point (Pa)	Flow point (Pa)	SR (%)
I-1:1-10	1288	510	0.393	0.994	840	727	0.86	114	561	51
I-1:1-10-CNF	1001	357	0.342	0.998	1520	1009	0.66	21	126	65
I-2:1-15	3678	1167	0.269	0.999	3308	2026	0.61	137	1860	35
I-2:1-15-CNF	6279	1798	0.202	0.995	8488	3498	0.41	42	2000	45

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 361

362 **Figure 4.** Rheological characterization of inks, (a) viscosity as a function of shear rate and (b) storage
 363 modulus (G') (solid symbols) and loss modulus (G'') (open symbols) as a function of shear stress.
 364

365 Similar to their mixture counterparts, inks also showed pseudoplastic behavior with flow index
 366 values in the range of 0-1, vital for a proper 3D printing process. The incorporation of *Salvia*
 367 caused an increase of viscosity and consistency index values when comparing both M-1:1-10 vs.
 368 I-1:1-10 and M-2:1-15 vs. I-2:1-15 (Table 1 and Table 3). This behavior was also observed by A.

369 Silva-Weiss et al. on chitosan and chitosan-starch blends with murta leaf extract [52]. On the other
370 hand, the change in flow index was less pronounced and did not follow a direct trend, in
371 accordance with literature reports [53]. Concerning the effect of solid content in rheology, I-2:1-
372 15 showed higher viscosity than I-1:1-10 in the studied shear rate range, presumably due to the
373 higher solid content of I-2:1-15, as previously commented. Unexpectedly, the incorporation of
374 CNF resulted in a reduction of zero-shear viscosity and consistency index values when comparing
375 I-1:1-10 and I-1:1-10-CNF. This would suggest that alginate-CNF interactions can compete with
376 alginate-water interactions, reducing the viscosity of the inks. A similar effect was observed by
377 Liu S. et al. [54] when analyzing graphene oxide-carrageenan hydrogels, reporting changes in
378 gelation ability of carrageenan in aqueous solution as a consequence of graphene-oxide
379 incorporation. Moreover, it is also reported in the literature that CNF incorporation can cause a
380 disruption on the alginate chain ordering [55]. Thus, it could be said that despite the hydrogen
381 bonding interactions occurring due to the presence of CNF [56, 57], they were not sufficient to
382 counteract the disrupted interactions and hence the viscosity of the system decreased. On the
383 contrary, on the inks with higher solid content, the incorporation of CNF resulted in a notorious
384 increase on viscosity and consistency index values when comparing I-2:1-15 and I-2:1-15-CNF.
385 This could be indicative that more hydrogen bonding interactions occurred, sufficient to counteract
386 the effect of the disrupted interactions. These results might suggest that I-2:1-15-CNF would offer
387 the best shape fidelity. In both I-1:1-10 and I-2:1-15, the incorporation of CNF caused a decrease
388 in flow index values, improving the pseudoplasticity and thus extrudability of the inks. Low flow
389 index values reflect the incapability of the system to reestablish interactions occurring at rest,
390 suggesting that CNF interfere on inks structure.

391 Apart from pseudoplasticity, G' and G'' values and the ratio between them are important
392 parameters when analyzing printability of inks [58]. To that end, spectromechanical analysis was
393 carried out by a shear stress sweep test (Figure 4b). All inks showed $G' > G''$ values, indicating a
394 solid-like behavior. According to literature, a minimum G' value of 10^3 Pa is required to obtain non
395 spreading and self-standing 3D structures [59]. Similarly, inks with G' values of 10^5 Pa might be
396 too stiff to be extruded [60]. I-1:1-10 showed a G' value of 840 Pa, below the theoretical minimum.
397 Comparing I-1:1-10 and I-2:1-15, it was observed that G' value increased, suggesting that I-2:1-15
398 would offer better shape fidelity and better ability to support the weight of deposited layers. Thus,
399 higher solid content in I-2:1-15 would have contributed to the increase of G' value. Furthermore,
400 the addition of CNF both in I-1:1-10-CNF and I-2:1-15-CNF resulted in an appropriate strategy to
401 increase G' values of the inks.

402 The ratio of G'' to G' is defined as the loss tangent ($\tan\delta$). To obtain good printability, a balance
403 should exist between the two modulus and a printability range can be defined. For example, T.
404 Gao et al. [61] determined a $\tan\delta$ range of 0.25-0.45 for satisfactory printing of alginate-gelatin
405 bioinks. In the case of alginate reinforced with polysaccharides such as CNF, a $\tan\delta$ range of
406 0.2-0.5 was proposed [37]. High $\tan\delta$ values, due to disproportionally high loss modulus, would
407 cause ink spreading upon deposition. On the contrary, low $\tan\delta$ values due to very high storage
408 modulus would result in non-uniformity of the filament and problems of cohesion between the
409 printed layers [61-63]. Considering this, 0.86 value determined for I-1:1-10 suggested that
410 material spreading problems could occur due to the predominance of viscous behavior rather
411 than elastic. The increase of solid content as well as the incorporation of CNF gave place to a
412 reduction of $\tan\delta$, suggesting that the formation of an elastic network was promoted rather than
413 viscous, and better shape fidelity would be achieved.

414 Yield point, defined as the stress where a drop in G' value occurs, is another parameter affecting
415 the printability of inks. I-1:1-10 and I-2:1-15 showed similar yield stress values, 114 Pa and
416 137 Pa, respectively. High yield stress values might favor shape fidelity [60]. However, it should
417 be taken into account that high yield stress values would result in high forces needed to extrude
418 the material [37], compromising the extrudability. It was observed that the incorporation of CNF
419 caused a decrease in yield point, thus lowering the pressure needed for printing and improving
420 extrudability. Moreover, as previously commented, the increase of G' values as a consequence
421 of CNF incorporation would also promote shape fidelity. Flow point values, determined at $G' = G''$,

422 showed the same tendency as viscosity values did. The low flow point value determined for
423 I-1:1-10-CNF and the relative proximity of yield and flow points may compromise shape fidelity
424 due to filament spreading. The results until now indicate that the rheological behavior of I 2:1-15
425 and specially I-2:1-15-CNF would be the most suitable for printing, with a good combination of
426 viscosity, extrudability and storage modulus.

427 The elastic recovery, that is, the ability of the inks to recover its original structure after being
428 subjected to high shear rates, was assessed by three-interval thixotropy test and results are
429 shown in Figure 5. When shear was applied, an instantaneous decrease of viscosity was
430 observed for all inks. This was indicative of flow ability, suggesting good suitability of the inks to
431 be processed by 3D printing. Subsequent to high shear interval, when shear ceased, inks showed
432 high viscosity values. The recovery percentage of each ink after 60 s was calculated and results
433 are shown in Table 3. Although recovery percentages were not very high, the high viscosity of
434 inks and adequate $\tan\delta$ values would contribute to shape fidelity and avoid ink spreading. It was
435 also observed that recovery percentages improved with CNF incorporation, suggesting a faster
436 recovery of CNF-based interactions. It is also worth noting that thanks to the significantly higher
437 initial viscosity of inks with 15 wt.% solid content, they were able to maintain higher viscosities
438 than inks with 10 wt.% after the high shear rate stage, despite their lower recovery values,
439 signaling to a better shape fidelity in 3D printing.

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Figure 5. Three-interval thixotropy test of inks

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3.4. Characterization of printed samples

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Photographs of 3D printed mesh and cylinder specimens are shown in Figure 6. When comparing mesh specimens printed with I-1:1-10 and I-2:1-15 inks, it could be said that I 2:1-15 gave place to a more detailed reproduction of CAD design, showing sharper edges. In the same fashion, a better ability to reproduce cylinder geometries was denoted. Thus, it could be said that I-2:1-15 provided better shape fidelity and self-standing ability. Phenomena like filament spreading and poor self-standing ability were observed when printing with ink I-1:1-10, probably due to the lower viscosity, consistency index and G' values, together with a higher $\tan\delta$ value, as commented previously. The structural recovery did not seem to be such a critical factor, since a value of 35% was measured for I-2:1-15 while for I-1:1-10 it was 51% (Table 3). With relation to the previously commented, the higher final viscosity values may be responsible for better shape fidelity and self-standing ability rather than structural recovery values.

When observing the effect of CNF incorporation in I-1:1-10, a more pronounced filament spreading effect was observed in the mesh specimen printed with I-1:1-10-CNF than its counterpart I-1:1-10. This effect was attributed to the lowering of viscosity and consistency index because of CNF incorporation together with a decrease in flow point, as reported previously. In contrast, CNF incorporation resulted in an improvement when printing cylinder specimens. This may suggest that the increase of G' and structural recovery, together with a decrease of $\tan\delta$ were responsible for a better self-standing ability shown by I-1:1-10-CNF. In the case of CNF

464 incorporation in I-2:1-15, it resulted in a general improvement of rheological properties, observing
 465 a satisfactory performance of the ink. Both mesh and cylinder specimens were printed with high
 466 shape fidelity and self-standing ability was also observed. Again, the notorious improvement of
 467 shape fidelity and self-standing ability observed for specimens printed with I-2:1-15-CNF when
 468 compared to specimens printed with I-1:1-10-CNF supported the idea that final viscosity values
 469 should be taken into account more than structural recovery values. This was in good agreement
 470 with the effect observed when comparing I-1:1-10 vs. I-1:1-10-CNF printed specimens.
 471

472 **Figure 6.** Photographs of 3D printed mesh and cylinder specimens (left), and CAD designs used to print the
 473 specimens (right).
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476 To analyze the impact of ink formulation over the mechanical performance of the printed parts,
 477 compressive mechanical analysis was carried out in cylinder specimens. Compressive properties
 478 were determined for cylinder specimens printed with I-1:1-10-CNF and I-2:1-15-CNF (Table 4)
 479 since no satisfactory parts, able to be tested, were printed with I-1:1-10 and I-2:1-15. It should be
 480 taken into account that inks are in viscous liquid state while parts comprise the solid component
 481 of the ink. In this way, mechanical performance of the parts could not be directly related with
 482 composition and rheological behavior of inks.
 483

484 **Table 4.** Mean and standard deviation values of compressive mechanical properties of cylinder specimens:
 485 elastic modulus (E), density, specific elastic modulus (E_{spec}), compressive strength (σ_c) and densification
 486 strain (ϵ_d)

Sample printing ink	E (MPa)	Density (g cm ⁻³)	E_{spec} (MPa)	σ_c (MPa)	ϵ_d (%)
I-1:1-10-CNF	4.4 ± 0.3	0.15 ± 0.01	29 ± 3	0.27 ± 0.04	48 ± 2
I-2:1-15-CNF	8.6 ± 1.2	0.16 ± 0.01	53 ± 7	0.98 ± 0.06	50 ± 2

487
 488
 489 Concerning the results, it was observed that parts printed with I 2:1-15-CNF showed remarkably
 490 higher compressive Young modulus values than parts printed with I-1:1-10-CNF. Specific Young
 491 modulus of cylinders printed with I-2:1-15-CNF was also notably higher, although the densities
 492 measured for specimens printed with both inks were very similar. These results evidenced the
 493 strong reinforcing effect of keratose. In good agreement with this, higher compressive strength
 494 was also determined for I-2:1-15-CNF derived cylinders. The densification strain marks the total
 495 collapse of porous structure and the beginning of a notorious increase in stress values, known as
 496 densification regime [65]. In this case, densification strain values were very similar for all samples,
 497 probably due to very similar density values [66].

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4. Conclusions

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501 Miscible keratose alginate systems were prepared by greenly extracted keratose and renewably
502 sourced alginate. It was observed that the increase of both total solid content and alginate content
503 resulted in an increase of viscosity. Fully biobased printable inks were satisfactorily prepared
504 containing keratose, alginate, salvia extracts and cellulose nanofibers. Concerning rheological
505 behavior, salvia incorporation caused an increase of viscosity. Furthermore, increasing solid
506 content resulted in an appropriate strategy to improve the printability of inks: viscosity and
507 consistency index increased and so did the storage modulus. Moreover, $\tan\delta$ value shifted to a
508 more balanced value between loss modulus and storage modulus. On the contrary, extrudability
509 was not improved. The incorporation of CNF did not cause the same effect in both inks viscosity,
510 so, the performance of CNF as an effective rheological modulator seems to be influenced by solid
511 content. However, it is to mention that the incorporation of CNF resulted in a general improvement
512 of storage modulus. The analysis of printed parts allowed assessing the impact of inks rheological
513 parameters over the shape fixity and self-standing ability. In general, it was concluded that
514 viscosity and $\tan\delta$ values were directly related with shape fixity. Moreover, storage modulus
515 showed to be a crucial factor when self-standing ability of inks was implied. In fact, only inks
516 containing CNF were able to print cylinder geometries, which was related to their high storage
517 modulus value. Keratose noticeably improved mechanical properties of the printed parts,
518 obtaining samples with higher Young modulus and compressive strength.

519

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521

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